

Qualitative Study on In - Service Teachers' Programme and Future Curriculum Implementation among Secondary Schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper assessed qualitative study of in - service teachers' programme and future curriculum implementation in secondary schools of Kaduna State. In - service training is important for a successful implementation and realization secondary education objectives in the study area. It remains the only option that allows every teacher to be re - trained and even acquire high knowledge on what would help to effectively implement school curriculum at this level of Nigeria' s education system. Secondary sources of data collection were adopted in this study. Of course, the paper was qualitative research in nature and have discussed the followings namely concepts of a teacher and teacher education, objectives of teacher education, future curriculum and implementation of secondary school curriculum viz-a-viz in - service teachers. Among the challenges teachers in Nigeria are faced with today includes poor self - study attitude and poor motivation which has beam a cog in the wheel of their professional growth. Absence of materials with which to work dampens the morale of teachers as also been identified as well as inability of some training institutions to develop in them skills and attitudes to explore avenues of updating their knowledge. A significant number of these teachers do not deem it necessary to set standards and device means of assessing their progress and failures with the view of making adjustments and innovations that can bring about improved performance. It thus concluded that in order to meet up with the future trend in the training of the learners, government at all levels should put on all necessary materials in place to educate our teachers who are the agent of change in the society. It recommended among others that government should make teacher education programme attractive in terms of provision of adequate facilities and other incentives that will revamp the entire programmes.

Keywords: Future curriculum, Implementation, In - Service Training, Secondary Education, Teacher Education

Introduction

Education is key for socio - economic empowerment and poverty reduction of a nation. It is thus the springboard for personal and societal progress and development (Omajoko, 2009). This means that for any meaningful progress and development to take place in any society, there should be a sound and functional system which will enhance personal and societal growth and development in all areas of human endeavour. In support of this, Odawn and Akpata (2008) believed that education is the key that unlocks the door to modernization. Teachers are the key factor that holds the key to this door. This implies that teachers are the agent of change in the society who can make the lofty ideas of the educational system a reality. The teacher translates the educational policies and programmes to bring about the needed changes in the society. In this respect, the learner is at the centre of all these and teacher on his part acts as the pilot of the educational process. The way the teacher thus interprets the curriculum will have a direct bearing on the level of training received after the pre - service training. Therefore, a well - trained teacher will bring about improved standard of education and consequently the general developmental process of the country. However, any teacher not trained via refresher course or what is referred to as in - service training would not be effective to implement the secondary school curriculum as much as is expected. This perhaps was the reason adduced that no education can rise above its teachers and that no nation can rise above its teachers. This paper will be of great benefit

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to the classroom teachers in the implementation of school curriculum, guide parents on how to their children are fairing and for the government, on the need to fund teacher education programme and to encourage more teachers to go for in - service training to update their professional knowledge from time to time and to the policy makers, in their policy formation as regards to teacher education programme not only in Kaduna State but Nigeria at large.

In-Service Teachers at the Secondary Schools

It is not everybody that handles a chalk before the learners that is regarded as a teacher. A teacher is that person who is capable of making rational human and creative decisions regarding the teaching act. In essence, teachers are mediator of learning, controller of students' behaviour, act as parent substitute, judge of achievement, curriculum developer, interpreter and researcher as public servant. In all these, they require adequate knowledge and skills to be able to undertake specific assignment bequeath to them in the line of duty. This form of education can be obtained through what is known as in - service education. In - service education can simply be defined as the relevant courses and activities in which a serving teacher may participate to upgrade his professional knowledge, skills, and competence in the teaching profession. Therefore, it encompasses all forms of education and training given to a teacher who is already on the job of teaching and learning. In - service education is also referred to as continuing education that is designed for the retraining, reskilling and updating the knowledge of manpower. According to UNESCO in Osamwonyi (2016) continuing education can be regarded as the entire body of educational processes whatever the content level and method, whether formal or otherwise, whether they prolong or replace initial education in schools, colleges and universities as well as in apprenticeship, whereby persons regarded as adults by the society to which they belong develop their abilities, enrich their knowledge, improve their technical or professional qualifications or turn them in a new direction and bring about changes in their attitudes or behaviour in the two fold perspective of full personal development and participation on balance and independent social, economic and cultural development.

The quality of teacher's performance at his/her duty post as a professional is an important thing to discuss, considering its significant role in secondary school curriculum implementation as evident in student achievement (Canales and Maldonado, 2018). But this role cannot be separated from the educational context, student characteristics, and school factors (Ambussaidi and Yang, 2019). In addition, the ability of teachers to be confident, create a comfortable climate for students, maintain interaction and contact with students can increase student involvement in learning (Durksen, Way, Bobis, Anderson, Skilling and Martin, 2017). Obviously, the higher the comfort of the teachers with the school, the increase its influence on their performance in the school (Sebastian, Herman and Reinke, 2019). While the pressure experienced by a teacher in a school that is sourced from various things and aspects will certainly reduce performance (Erichsen and Reynolds, 2019). The low performance of students in secondary schools, dynamic society and its needs, continues changes in expectations about the quality and assessment of education, rapid changes in science and technology lead the school and teachers to face difficulties with this respect to parents and society. In fact, the issues for teachers and teachers' education to fulfill these requirements are continuing and complex (Moeini in Medard, 2017).

In-Service Teacher Education Programme

In - service teacher training has grown in importance and status and has developed as a global trend for decades. Public organizations like schools try to increase their capabilities by investing more in employees (teacher) training. Moreover, it encourages competency of employees (teachers) for both their own benefit and the benefit of others (Rodrigues in Medard, 2017). In a career system, initial training is of paramount in the effective and efficient work performance. The newly recruited employees enter into an establishment without specific expertise for the job (Fraser cited by Medard, 2017). In fact, initial training offers general preparation in public service delivery. Such training offers specific preparation for a new function after or before transfer or promotion. Although, it is clear that in - service training programmes for employee (teachers) on work performance are increasingly drawing attention in public organization in view of their under - performance (URT, 2012). The fact is, it is no longer sufficient to recruit and retains the best employees but, organizations have to impart skills and enhance their capabilities through learning, supportive environment and shared knowledge. The quality of employees through training programs is the major factors in determining long term success of public organizations.

"Teachers" in the educational process refers to the person who instructs and promote the teaching-learning processes. He assumes various capacities as educator, instructor, tutor, lecturer, counsellor and so on. Whereas, education on the other hand is defined as a tool used for the integration of individuals into the society so that he/she can achieve self - realization, develop national consciousness, promote unity and strive for social, economic, political, scientific, cultural and technological progress. Teacher education therefore is that aspect of education which deals with the acquisition of practical and applied skills

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in the teaching profession (Apeh, 2010). This means that teacher education can be viewed to as professional education of teachers towards attainment of attitudes, skill and knowledge considered desirable so as to make them efficient and effective in their work in accordance with the needs of the society at any point in time. A good teacher educational programme must assist the individual teacher to grow and develop as a person, provide him with the necessary skills and professional competence that will assist him to become not only an effective teacher but also enviable community leader that will be able to project into future in terms of new trends in teaching and learning process.

Future Curriculum at Secondary Education

Future curriculum is an attempt to project into the future based on the past and present events or happening towards the type of education the learners may receive in order to prepare them for the likely changes that may occur in the nearer future. It is a design or planning of the whole education programme for the betterment of a future society (Saedah and Mohammed, 2003). Therefore, future curriculum is developed today for tomorrow based on systematic forecasting of what the system should be. Siraj (2015) identified two (2) main elements of concern in future curriculum to include: identifying main events with high probabilities to happen in the future - related to education for future society; and forecasting on various analysis dimension which relates to education for future society which include analysis on socio-economic politics, human resources, energy sources, agriculture. Future curriculum emerged as a result of study on future probabilities within a certain time frame. Analysis as carried out to ascertain how particular phenomenon have affected the results of policy implementation or action taken by a country (Longstreet and Shane 2009). This implies that it is a systematic and technical study of the knowledge of past and present conditions with the aim of predicting and designing what would happen in the future. The aim according to Glenn and Garden (2008) as applicable to this work among others include to:

1. Assist policy makers and curriculum developers of institution and the country to outline action plans in order to avoid making false assumptions about the future curriculum of our schools.
2. Illustrate possibilities and choices about the future to aid policy makers and curriculum developers of institutions and country to their attempts to make critical decisions and
3. Explain probabilities of preferred futures. In a nutshell future curriculum is viewed as systematic discipline to study probable future within a certain time frame. More so, analysis is carried out to ascertain how particular situations and environment could be affected as a result of policy implementation.

In-Service Teachers on Implementation of Future Curriculum at the Secondary Schools

1. Information Acquisition

The inevitability of this strategy hinges on the premise that the wider the range of opportunities known to an individual, the wiser his choice will become and the wider the horizon of knowledge will be. Thus, as a professional, a teacher's learning (acquisition of current information) should continue throughout his life time. This is contrary to the assumption that teacher practically completed his systematic learning as soon as the coveted certificate is obtained. This strategy hinges on the assumption that the teacher's own systematic learning is only well started when he graduates from his formal programme of teaching training. Teacher education should aim at instilling the attitude of continuous learning throughout his life. Emphasis of teacher education should be on assisting the student-teacher knows how to plan his own systematic learning. Concern of strategy is to help build up the learner's informational background as well assisting the teacher to develop the attitude, skills and abilities necessary to continuously increase and appraise his store of information while still on the job. The modern teacher needs and deserves adequate preparation to continue systematic learning following the completion of his formal course. Buttressing this necessity, Onuh (2009) posits thus:

There are many reasons why the modern teacher cannot afford to stop growing professionally once he gets on the job in the first place, stagnation may lead to grumping, unhappiness, and irritation... there is danger that continuous repetition of the same assignments and discussions will make the teaching job a boring one instead of the challenging one it can be.

Information acquisition can make teaching a very pleasant and exhilarating experience. It gives satisfaction to the teacher and serves as a model for the students to emulate. Learners quickly catch the enthusiasm of a teacher who is constantly growing in knowledge and in its use. Accordingly, professional magazines, journals and books offer an excellent resource for meeting the desire of a professional teacher who must keep abreast of current thinking in his field of specialization. Perhaps this is what informed Ogbe (2010) to postulate that: "For those who work on the growing edge of science.... Only a few months may elapse before something which was easily taken for granted must be unlearned or transformed to fit the new state of knowledge."

In the light of this, it behooves those who teach and use knowledge keep abreast with new knowledge in their fields. Through professional acquisition of information, teachers can find solutions to their professional growth, which if left unchecked may inhibit their professional growth in terms of facilitating learning.

2. Appraisal Technique

This strategy deals with the analysis and interpretation of all valid data and information about an individual for the purpose of understanding in terms of his interests, aptitudes, capability and personality. Through this device, an individual's assets and liabilities are understood. To set the stage for systematic change in activities that will culminate in improvement, it is desirable for the teacher to continually diagnose what he is doing why he is doing, and how it is succeeding. The assumption here is that the changes of happiness and success as a teacher enhanced by continuous self-diagnosis. Some of the potent approaches to embark upon in order to identify teacher's assets and liabilities for the purpose of teaching are: comparative check on personal efficiency using one teaching method versus efficiency in using another method, voluntary and continuing colleague discussion or seminar by teachers of a particular course, visiting a colleague class for the purpose of evaluating and improving personal performance, self-constructed evaluative questionnaire or check lists to be filled by students and soliciting the assistance of supervisors in evaluating personal teaching.

3. Evaluation Strategy

Following a period of functioning, any professional would want to ascertain the degree of success or failures. Systematic evaluation in the classroom has long been seen as the exclusive responsibilities of the teacher. Such control of evaluative processes has resulted to extreme students dependence on the teacher for evaluative activities. It has led to learner being equipped to evaluate for learning purpose which involve practice in setting up goals, diagnosing needs through measurement, and in planning future activities.

4. Interpersonal Relationship

It has been assumed by too many teachers that the only measure front for improvement of professional activities was in the classroom. The current thinking is that there are many key areas outside the classroom where potentialities are bound for professional enhancement. For instance, an atmosphere of cooperation among teachers and attitudes sharing ideas and materials can enhance the art teaching. In fact, interpersonal relationships are skills that individuals need to become competent helpers (Abah, 2009). Teachers are facilitators of learning. They need interpersonal relationship skills to mature professionally. Abah (2009), remarks that most difficult problems in living are interpersonal in nature. It becomes necessary therefore to help individuals develop the skills needed for establishing and maintaining effective interpersonal relationship. For any successful teaching-learning and/or implementing situation, the individuals concerned must have a well - developed repertory of interpersonal skills. Teachers need the skills to learn about themselves and others because they are teachers of others and not just part of the curriculum. Abah (2009) contend that the starting point for education is the need for self - development as a person. This enables the teacher become someone who is competent to help others develop.

Challenges of Pre - Service Teachers in the future Curriculum Delivery at Secondary Schools in Kaduna State

A good number of practicing teachers in Nigeria today possess poor self - study attitude. Their dispositions towards research leave much to be desired. This can be attributed to the wrong notion that learning ends at graduation and that knowledge thus acquired is sufficient to allow for maximum performance on their jobs. To such teacher, knowledge is not dynamic, hence to engage in further search for current information is a mere waste of time. The problem is further compounded by the inability of some training institutions to develop in them skills and attitudes to explore avenues of updating their knowledge. Thus, the majority of today's teachers erroneously think they have acquired enough for life in the college. This general apathy towards self -improvement extended to workshops, seminars and conferences. Hardly to teachers avail themselves of these opportunities to acquire professional skills for optimal performance. The result is stagnation in professional growth which should not be allowed into the 21st century. There is a general lack of basic skills in self - appraisal by teachers. A significant number of teachers do not deem it necessary to set standards and device means of assessing their progress and failures with the view of making adjustments and innovations that can bring about improved performance.

Equally noticed today is the wrong perception of learning as teacher curriculum centered is opposed to child - centered, Hence the child's interest and needs plays a secondary role in guiding the course of teaching - learning in most schools. Education should be seen as child - centered and all teaching - learning activities should revolve around this philosophy. Ability to make realistic decision is an important asset to any individual. Unfortunately, many teachers are handicapped to train students for decision-making processes. To such teachers, decision-making is an exclusive responsibility of the adult on behalf of the

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child. The child therefore grows up ill - equipped to make realistic decision and accept responsibility for whatever the aftermath would be.

Record keeping systems of contemporary teachers leave much desired. Professional teachers should be able not only to acquire data but also, competent enough to store, retrieve and utilize such data for decision making and assessing personal growth in their profession. Closely allied to the above is the poor and unprofessional practice of continuous assessment by some teachers. Many have not come to terms with the implications of continuous assessment. Worst still, a significant number of teachers are ill-equipped to continuously assess students. Cognitive, as opposed to psychomotor and effective domains inclusive appears to be the only area of assessment. Even then, continuous assessment ought to be teacher-oriented and not just for labeling students. An area that has constituted a cog in the wheel of professional growth of teachers is motivation. Absence of materials with which to work dampens the morale of teachers, hence hindering their desire to improve themselves professionally. Teachers need motivation, recognition and appreciation to grow professionally in the practice of teaching. Against the backdrop of the current professional status of the teacher, counseling strategies are advanced to improve the practice of teaching by professional teachers in the 21st century (Ogbe, 2010).

Conclusion

Future curriculum is very vital in policy making and curriculum development at all educational level of an institution and country in general. In order to embrace new education policies and implementation of curriculum content for future delivery, there is the need for restructuring of teacher education programme in Nigeria to significantly prepare educators. Since teachers that are Nigerian educators are agents of change in the society. There is every need to train and retrain them in order to meet up with the future trends in the training of the learners, government at all levels should put on all necessary materials in place to educate our teachers who are the agents of change in the society.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should be trained and retrained from time to time in the area of school activities' assessments and evaluation in order to take advantage of the past and current trends in teaching and learning process to project into the likely future changes in the needs of the learner and society;
2. Curriculum planners and educational policy makers should provide a structure for teachers in their different disciplines the correct instrument for assessing and evaluating their learners with view of changes in the curriculum; and
3. Teacher education programmes should be adequately funded, in order for the pre-service and in-service teachers should be acquainted with necessary skills in assessing and evaluating students' academic progress in view of currents trends in teaching and learning process in relation to future changes in learners and society needs.

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